

The Ruler

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Abstract

A cell deciding what to become, a neural network generalising to unseen data, and an evolving population producing open-ended novelty face the same problem. Each must stay viable under futures it has not yet encountered. I show that the formal quantity governing all three is the same. It is “weakness”, defined as the number of completions compatible with a system’s current commitments in an embodied language. Survival probability is exponential in the number of compatible futures. Applied to basal cognition, weakness gives a formal ruler for Levin’s cognitive light cones. Applied to machine learning, it reframes dropout, double descent, grokking, and transferability as cone-width phenomena, and exposes flat minima as an encoding-dependent shadow of the real quantity. Applied to artificial life, it says open-ended evolution requires slack at every layer of a multiscale system, not just variation at the top. Three communities have been measuring the same thing without knowing it.

Introduction

Three research communities care about the same problem without sharing a language for it.

In basal cognition, Levin and collaborators describe cognitive light cones, the spatiotemporal boundary of goals a system can pursue (Levin, 2019, 2021, 2022; Lyons et al., 2026; Solé et al., 2026). The cone can grow, shrink, merge, and fail. Cancer can be framed as cone shrinkage. Alignment might be framed as cone overlap. But the framework has not yet specified a formal size variable. We can say one cone is bigger without entirely specifying what “bigger” means.

In machine learning, the central problem is generalisation (LeCun et al., 2015). Given training data, which model will perform best on data it has not yet seen? Decades of work have produced candidate measures, from VC dimension (Vapnik and Chervonenkis, 1971) to flat minima (Hochreiter and Schmidhuber, 1997) to PAC-Bayes bounds (McAllester, 1999; Neyshabur et al., 2017). None reliably predict generalisation across all settings (Jiang et al., 2020). Most are encoding-dependent. Reparameterise the same function and the measure changes (Dinh et al., 2017).

In artificial life, the aspiration is open-ended evolution (Langton, 1995; Packard et al., 2019; Bedau, 2003). How

can a system keep producing novelty indefinitely without collapsing into a fixed repertoire? The question is clear enough, but the formal criterion for when a system is open-ended is less so.

I show that that three domains have the same problem, and same answer. Same ruler, to be specific. The formal quantity that governs survival under novelty, generalisation to unseen data, and sustained production of new forms is the “weakness” of constraints on function. Weakness counts how many future commitments remain compatible with a system’s current commitments in an embodied language. It is proved necessary and sufficient for optimal generalisation under a maximally uninformative prior, and minimax optimal under exchangeable priors (Bennett, 2025b,a, 2026a). Survival probability is exponential in the number of compatible futures (Proposition 1), and the rest of the paper builds on that to explore how this can be applied across 3 different domains.

The formal quantity

Weakness is derived from Stack Theory. Stack Theory is a minimalist framework designed to avoid making assumptions about substrate, symbols, or Turing machines. The philosophical justifications for these definitions are covered elsewhere (Bennett, 2025a, 2024a, 2025b). The core definition is an “environment”, which is a nonempty set Φ of mutually exclusive states, each representing a change or distinction from other states rather than any particular ontological or semantic content. A program is then any nonempty subset $p \subseteq \Phi$, and a finite vocabulary \mathfrak{v} is a set of such programs. It induces an embodied language

$$L_{\mathfrak{v}} = \left\{ l \subseteq \mathfrak{v} \mid \bigcap_{p \in l} p \neq \emptyset \right\}.$$

A vocabulary is what a body can distinguish, so it formalises a quotient, coarse graining or “abstraction layer” over the lower level environment. A “language” is what that body can consistently say. This is not a symbolic language (Harnad, 1990), but a set of embodied constraints determined by the body’s physical relationship to its environment (Varela et al.,

2016; Thompson, 2007; Pfeifer and Bongard, 2007). Put another way, a body is under-specified, and the embodied language is all the ways we might complete its specification. Asserting some embodied statement translates down to a constraints on the underlying environment states.

Definition 1 (Extension and weakness). *For any policy $\pi \in L_v$, define its extension by $\text{Ext}(\pi) = \{y \in L_v \mid \pi \subseteq y\}$. For any set of statements $A \subseteq L_v$, define $\text{Ext}(A) = \bigcup_{a \in A} \text{Ext}(a)$. The weakness of π is $w(\pi) = |\text{Ext}(\pi)|$.*

The extension is the set of further commitments still compatible with the commitments already made. Weakness counts how many such continuations remain. This is a property of function in an embodied language. If simplicity is a property of form (the policy), then weakness is a property of function (what the policy does). It is not a property of how short the description looks to an observer (Bennett, 2024b).

Definition 2 (Task and correct policy). *A v -task is a pair $\alpha = \langle I_\alpha, O_\alpha \rangle$ where $I_\alpha, O_\alpha \subseteq L_v$ and $O_\alpha \subseteq \text{Ext}(I_\alpha)$. A policy π is correct for α if $\text{Ext}(I_\alpha) \cap \text{Ext}(\pi) = O_\alpha$. Write Π_α for the set of correct policies.*

A task specifies inputs and the outputs they should produce. Each task is a definition of “correct”. Given a particular task, a correct policy is one whose commitments, combined with the input constraints, yield only the task outputs.

Fix a task α with input set I_α . Write the unseen region as $U := L_v \setminus \text{Ext}(I_\alpha)$. The unseen buffer is $\mathcal{B}(\pi) := \text{Ext}(\pi) \cap U$.

Proposition 1 (Survival under novelty). *Assume a currently correct policy π . Assume future requirements take the form of a novelty set $S \subseteq U$ drawn uniformly from 2^U . Assume π survives exactly when $S \subseteq \mathcal{B}(\pi)$. Then*

$$\mathbb{P}(\text{survive} \mid \pi) = 2^{|\mathcal{B}(\pi)| - |U|}.$$

Proof. Exactly $2^{|\mathcal{B}(\pi)|}$ subsets of U are subsets of $\mathcal{B}(\pi)$. There are $2^{|U|}$ subsets in total. Divide. \square

Every extra compatible unseen outcome doubles survival probability (Bennett, 2026g). For currently correct policies, $\text{Ext}(\pi) \cap \text{Ext}(I_\alpha) = O_\alpha$ is fixed by the correctness condition, so $|\text{Ext}(\pi)| = |O_\alpha| + |\mathcal{B}(\pi)|$. Ranking by $|\mathcal{B}(\pi)|$ is therefore equivalent to ranking by $w(\pi)$. This is the ruler.

This is not an appeal to simplicity, because simplicity is encoding-dependent (Kolmogorov, 1965; Rissanen, 1978; Grünwald, 2007). Change the reference machine and the simplicity ranking changes (Hutter, 2005; Leike and Hutter, 2015). Weakness depends on the embodied vocabulary, which is fixed by the body’s physical relationship to its environment. If a persisting object is simple, that is incidental unless it is also weak (Bennett, 2024b). The whole point of Stack Theory is to disambiguate simplicity of form from generalisation of function. While this approach is somewhat unconventional, it has already yielded significant empirical

results such as more sample efficient logical program induction Bennett (2025a) and a representation invariant alternative to flat minima in machine learning Bennett (2026a).

Two properties of weakness

Proposition 2 (Commitment-capacity dissociation). *For any finite vocabulary v with $|v| \geq 2$, there exist policies $\pi_1, \pi_2 \in L_v$ with $\pi_1 \supseteq \pi_2$ such that $w(\pi_1) = 1$ and $w(\pi_2) = |L_v|$.*

Proof. Since $|v| \geq 2$ and each singleton $\{p\}$ is in L_v , the language has at least three elements and admits maximal elements that are nonempty. Let π_1 be any maximal element of L_v . Then $\text{Ext}(\pi_1) = \{\pi_1\}$ and $w(\pi_1) = 1$. Let $\pi_2 = \emptyset$. Then $\text{Ext}(\pi_2) = L_v$ and $w(\pi_2) = |L_v|$. Since $\pi_1 \neq \emptyset$, $\pi_1 \supseteq \pi_2$. \square

One embodied language can express two systems with maximally different weaknesses. The body determines the vocabulary of this language, and weakness depends on how much of that vocabulary has been committed. A system that has committed to everything has a cone of size one. A system that has committed to nothing has the largest possible cone. Commitment and adaptive capacity pull in opposite directions.

Proposition 3 (Basin width bounds adaptive capacity). *Let $B \subseteq L_v$ be a nonempty set of policies (a basin). Define the basin policy $\pi_B = \bigcap_{\pi \in B} \pi$. Then $\pi_B \in L_v$, $B \subseteq \text{Ext}(\pi_B)$, and $w(\pi_B) \geq |B|$. For any $\pi' \supseteq \pi_B$, $w(\pi') \leq w(\pi_B)$. Every additional commitment beyond π_B can only shrink the cone.*

Proof. For any $\pi \in B$, $\pi_B \subseteq \pi$, so $\bigcap_{p \in \pi_B} p \supseteq \bigcap_{p \in \pi} p \neq \emptyset$, giving $\pi_B \in L_v$. Also $\pi \in \text{Ext}(\pi_B)$, so $B \subseteq \text{Ext}(\pi_B)$. Therefore $w(\pi_B) \geq |B|$. For $\pi' \supseteq \pi_B$, any $y \in \text{Ext}(\pi')$ satisfies $y \supseteq \pi' \supseteq \pi_B$, so $y \in \text{Ext}(\pi_B)$. Thus $\text{Ext}(\pi') \subseteq \text{Ext}(\pi_B)$. \square

The weakness of a homeostatic system is determined by the width of its basin. A thermostat with a wide temperature band has a large $|B|$ and therefore a large cone, while a thermostat with a narrow band has a small one.

Scaling across layers

Write $T(\pi) = \bigcap_{p \in \pi} p$ for the truth set of a policy.

Theorem 1 (The Law of the Stack (Bennett, 2024a, 2025a)). *Let adjacent layers i and $i + 1$ satisfy $v^{i+1} = \{T(o) \mid o \in \text{Ext}(\pi^i)\}$, where π^i is the realised policy at layer i and α^{i+1} is the induced task at layer $i + 1$. Then*

$$\sup_{\pi \in \Pi_{\alpha^{i+1}}} w(\pi) \leq 2^{|\text{Ext}(\pi^i)|}.$$

The weakness of any correct policy at layer $i + 1$ cannot exceed 2 raised to the weakness at layer i . Higher-layer adaptive capacity cannot exceed the room left open below.

Instantiation

Here is how the formalism maps to concrete systems. Consider a layer of three binary neurons. The vocabulary is $\mathbf{v} = \{p_1, \dots, p_8\}$ where each p_i is the set of inputs producing activation pattern i . The language $L_{\mathbf{v}}$ has at most $2^8 = 256$ statements. A policy that has committed to a specific pattern (say $\{p_3\}$) has a small extension. A policy that has committed to nothing (\emptyset) has weakness $|L_{\mathbf{v}}|$. Weakness is computable here. In large networks exact computation is combinatorially expensive, but cheaper approximations or “proxies” have proven effective (Bennett, 2026a, 2025a).

In a cell, the vocabulary is the set of distinguishable physiological or bioelectric states the cell can occupy. Each state p is the set of environmental conditions under which it is viable. A cell locked into a narrow developmental fate has a small extension, while a pluripotent cell has a large one.

What the ruler measures

The ruler counts compatible futures. Some intuition as to what this means is given through a musical analogy, where space is a chord and time is an arpeggio Bennett (2026b). Time is sequentially realised distinction and space is simultaneously realised distinction, but both are counts of one underlying resource. A system’s adaptive capacity can appear as spatial breadth, temporal depth, or a tradeoff between them (Bennett, 2026e).

Application 1: Cognitive light cones

A cognitive light cone (Levin, 2019) is the spatiotemporal boundary of goals a system can pursue. The concept is part of a broader programme treating cognition as scale-free and substrate-general (Fields and Levin, 2020; McMillen and Levin, 2024). In the present formalism, I take the “cone” of a policy π is to be its extension, so $\mathcal{C}(\pi) := \text{Ext}(\pi)$ and cone size is $w(\pi)$. Levin’s programme defines the cone as the spatiotemporal scale of goals a system can pursue, whereas weakness is a formal measure that determines survival under novelty. These are closely related but not quite identical, and the differences do have some impact in the cases below.

What the ruler supports

Cancer as cone shrinkage is already well modelled by Stack Theory. If parts $1, \dots, m$ have feasible policy sets Π_1, \dots, Π_m , a collective identity exists only when $\bigcap_{j=1}^m \Pi_j \neq \emptyset$ (Bennett, 2024a). When constraints drive this intersection to the empty set, the collective has fragmented (Levin, 2021; Davies and Lineweaver, 2011). Tumour formation can be understood as a downscaling of the self (Levin, 2021). Existing Stack Theory results perfectly align with this idea (Bennett, 2024a) and extend it with a falsifiable criterion, which is that collapse is the disappearance of the collective feasible set. Future work might measure this empirically, in bioelectric experiments by tracking whether inter-

ventions that restore membrane voltage patterns also restore a nonempty policy intersection.

Cone scaling via collective integration is also neatly formalised by the Law of the Stack. Levin argues that multicellularity and bioelectric coordination enlarge the cognitive boundary (Levin, 2019, 2022). The Law of the Stack offers a formal mathematical explanation of why and how this is the case. Lower layers delegate adaptation instead of freezing it. Higher-layer cones grow only when lower layers retain slack. This also formalises the management cybernetics principle that viable systems must grant autonomy to their subsystems (Beer, 1995). In the language of Solé et al. (2019), solid brains achieve this through persistent high-bandwidth wiring, while liquid brains achieve it through slower interactions among mobile agents. Both are delegation strategies. McShea (2002) observed that the transition to multicellularity involves a complexity drain on individual cells, trading cellular autonomy for collective capability. In Stack Theoretic terms, that trade is the cost of widening the collective cone. It is a neat formal analogue for what past work has argued qualitatively with respect to lightcones.

Nested identities in Levin’s programme also get a neat formal analogue. They correspond to stacks of abstraction layers in Stack Theory (Bennett, 2025a). Alignment as a homeostatic problem (Lyons et al., 2026) becomes the task of engineering constraints weak enough to preserve a non-empty intersection of component policy sets. The basal cognition literature (Lyon, 2006, 2015; Barandiaran et al., 2009) argues that cognitive capacities extend far below the neural threshold, into single cells, tissues, and molecular networks. Nothing in the formalism requires neurons, just a vocabulary and an embodied language, so this idea is also well defined.

What the ruler qualifies

While there are many synergies, it must be said that my ruler does not quite *perfectly* align with the cognitive lightcone as originally proposed. There are a few small but manageable differences.

By Proposition 2, commitment and adaptive capacity pull in opposite directions within any fixed vocabulary. A maximally committed policy has weakness 1 regardless of how large the vocabulary is. More broadly, cone size depends on how much of the vocabulary has been committed, not on how large the vocabulary is. It has been suggested a system with a large body and broad sensing has a large cone, but in Stack Theory a large vocabulary with rigid commitments has a tiny cone. Broad sensing and body size in this sense determine the vocabulary, but cone size depends on what the body does with it (and that can vary wildly with policy choice).

Another way my framework seems to diverge from Levin’s is in upper bounds on cone size. Previous work places no explicit upper bound on cone size (Levin, 2019). The Law of the Stack supplies one at every layer, which clarifies what must be loosened for a cone to grow.

By Proposition 3, adaptive capacity is basin width, not homeostatic success. A system that converges to a single state has $|B| = 1$ and minimal weakness. A system that converges to a basin with many viable states has weakness at least $|B|$. The drive to reduce stress is adaptive only insofar as the target is a basin rather than a point. Biological systems under selection for resilience should evolve wider basins, not just stronger convergence (Di Paolo, 2000). Agosta et al. (2010) documented a biological instance of this, showing that parasites with “sloppy fitness” (wide host-range basins) are better positioned to colonise novel hosts.

For agency, cones can scale upward across collectives and hybrids (Solé et al., 2026). For unified subjectivity, a spacetime bound still applies. If a conscious moment requires co-instantiation and within-window causal exchange, then the support diameter D is bounded by $D \leq v\theta h(G)/2$, where v is the signal speed ceiling, θ is the integration window, and $h(G)$ is the hop diameter of the exchange graph (Bennett, 2026b,d). Returning to my musical analogy; agency can be arpeggiated, but notions like unity in consciousness may require a chord.

Application 2: Machine learning

A trained model is a policy. The training data constrains it. The extension of that policy is the set of further data assignments still compatible with what the model has learned. A model that has overfit has committed to specific training examples. Its cone is narrow. A model that has learned general features has committed to less. Its cone is wide. Proposition 1 says the second model is exponentially more likely to survive novel data.

The Law of the Stack applies to deep networks. Higher-layer generalisation is bounded by lower-layer slack. If early layers commit too tightly to training-specific features, later layers cannot compensate.

Flat minima are a shadow of weakness

The claim that flat minima indicate better generalisation goes back to Hochreiter and Schmidhuber (1997). Sharpness-aware minimisation explicitly penalises sharp minima during training (Foret et al., 2021). But Dinh et al. (2017) showed that sharp minima can be made flat by reparameterisation without changing the function. The geometry is not invariant. Petzka et al. (2021) proposed relative flatness to address this, but the underlying problem remains. The measure depends on the parameterisation. Weakness does not. It is defined over the function, not the parameterisation, and so I have argued in a related machine learning paper that flat minima debate is a debate about the wrong quantity (Bennett, 2026a).

Recent work has also connected generalisation to compression. Del’etang et al. (2023) showed that language modelling is compression, and compression is intimately related to description length (Shannon, 1948; Rissanen, 1978). But description length is encoding-dependent in the same way

flatness is. Weakness avoids this because it is defined over the embodied vocabulary, not over a coding scheme. Generalisation is about function, not form.

Connecting ML to cones via weakness

Weakness offers explanations for various machine learning phenomena, and we can thus connect from machine learning to weakness to lightcones.

Dropout (Srivastava et al., 2014) prevents co-adaptation of features. In cone terms, it prevents the model from committing to training-specific conjunctions, which means the trained policy tends to be weaker.

Double descent (Nakkiran et al., 2020) occurs because the interpolation threshold forces the model into a single completion of the training data. Below and above that threshold, multiple completions remain available. The cone is narrow at the threshold and “widens” on either side.

Grokking (Power et al., 2022) is the delayed emergence of generalisation after memorisation. Memorisation is commitment to specific input-output pairs. Continued training finds a weaker policy that covers the same data with a larger extension. Grokking is the model discovering that a weaker policy exists.

Yosinski et al. (2014) showed that early layers learn general features and later layers learn task-specific features. The Law of the Stack predicts this. Lower layers that retain slack enable higher-layer adaptation, and transferability is an instance of delegation.

The generalisation measures literature has produced dozens of candidate predictors (Jiang et al., 2020; Neyshabur et al., 2017; McAllester, 1999; Dziugaite and Roy, 2017). No single measure reliably predicts generalisation across all settings. Weakness offers a candidate explanation. Most existing measures are defined over parameters or parameter-space geometry, and are therefore encoding-dependent. A measure defined over the function (weakness) should be more stable across architectures, though its full operationalisation in large-scale networks remains open (Bennett, 2026a).

Bengio et al. (2013) argued that the key challenge in representation learning is disentangling factors of variation, and others extended this to say the right inductive biases for higher-level cognition include modularity and sparse causal structure (Goyal and Bengio, 2022). In Stack Theory terms, a representation is a vocabulary. Disentangled representations are vocabularies whose programs have large, overlapping truth sets. They support wide cones.

Some have argued that causal representation learning requires representations that support interventions (Schölkopf et al., 2021). Bengio et al. (2020) formalised a meta-transfer objective for disentangling causal mechanisms. The causal identity result shows that weakness-maximised policies converge to representations that separate self-caused from externally caused change (Bennett, 2023, 2025a). The right representation for causal reasoning is the one that keeps the

Levin-style claim	Verdict	What weakness adds
The self has a computational boundary and a larger cone means more cognition (Levin, 2019, 2022).	Supported, with a caveat.	“Larger” means greater weakness, not merely larger geometry.
Cancer is shrinkage of the self (Levin, 2021).	Strongly supported.	Collapse is the collective feasible policy intersection becoming empty.
Multicellular coordination scales cognition (Levin, 2019, 2022; Solé et al., 2026).	Supported.	The Law of the Stack explains why. Higher-layer growth requires lower-layer slack.
Stress reduction drives cone expansion (Levin, 2019).	Qualified.	Adaptive capacity is basin width, not convergence strength.
Goal scale indicates cone size.	Dissociation.	Grand goals via rigid strategy means a narrow cone.
Cones can keep scaling in collectives and hybrids.	Qualified.	For agency, yes. For unified subjectivity, chord constraints apply.

Table 1: Where the ruler supports Levin, where it qualifies him, and where it dissociates a bit.

most interventional futures open, and this has been extended to reinforcement learning as well Bennett (2026c); Nayebi (2026).

One might also reframe things in the other direction. Regularisation, dropout, and early stopping could be seen as cone-widening interventions. They prevent premature commitment. Levin’s programme predicts that analogous interventions in biological systems should widen cognitive light cones. Bioelectric state changes can normalise tumours and redirect morphogenesis (Levin, 2021). In the present formalism, those would be cone-widening interventions. If their functional effect parallels regularisation in a neural network, that is evidence that this shared formal structure holds up.

Application 3: Open-ended evolution

Open-ended evolution asks how a system can keep producing novelty indefinitely (Langton, 1984, 1995; Packard et al., 2019; Bedau, 2003). Ruiz-Mirazo et al. (2004) defined life as autonomous systems with open-ended evolutionary capacities, which weakness can serve to measure.

Definition 3 (Open-endedness). *Fix a vocabulary v . An evolving system with collective policy $\pi_t \in L_v$ and collective cone $\mathcal{C}(\pi_t)$ at generation t is open-ended if $w(\pi_t)$ is non-decreasing. It is collapsing if $w(\pi_t)$ is eventually strictly decreasing.*

Autonomy is a non-empty collective identity. If parts $1, \dots, m$ have feasible policy sets Π_1, \dots, Π_m , autonomy requires $\bigcap_{j=1}^m \Pi_j \neq \emptyset$. Open-endedness is a non-shrinking cone. Each generation must leave at least as many compatible futures open as the last.

The Law of the Stack adds a structural constraint. If lower-level mechanisms become overconstrained, higher-level novelty is bottlenecked regardless of selection pressure. Open-ended evolution requires slack at every layer, not just variation at the top (Kauffman, 1993; Ikegami, 1999).

Three conditions are necessary for persistence. First, the

extension must include its own maintenance. The closure to efficient causation described by Rosen (1991) is a structural condition on the extension. A companion paper Bennett and Suzuki (2026) proves this formally as The Autopoietic Theorem, deriving organisational closure from weakness maximisation in Stack Theory. Others Eigen and Schuster (1979) have shown that hypercyclic organisation can sustain replication in the face of error, and Fontana and Buss (1994) demonstrated that self-maintaining organisations in artificial chemistries (Dittrich et al., 2001) can arise before selection acts on them. Why persistence selects for self-producing organisation in the first place is addressed by a companion paper (Bennett, 2026f), which derives the bias from the persistence ordering itself. Second, the autopoietic boundary (Maturana and Varela, 1980; Varela, 1975; Moreno and Mossio, 2015) must persist. Beer (2004) studied autopoiesis in the Game of Life. Cone collapse is the loss of self-maintenance. Third, the system must support variation. Sayama and Nehaniv (2025) showed that self-reproducing structures in cellular automata can undergo variation and selection, and homeostatic regulation at the population level (Watson and Lovelock, 1983) can maintain the collective cone through environmental perturbation. Walker and Davies (2013) argued that informational architecture distinguishes life from non-life. England (2013) derived thermodynamic bounds on self-replication. Both point to self-replication and self-maintenance as foundational to the chemistry-biology transition.

Bongard and Levin (2023) argued that biological systems are evolved, overloaded, multi-scale machines. The Law of the Stack provides the formal underpinning. A component that serves many functions has committed to less than one that serves one. It is weaker, and therefore more adaptive.

An artificial life agenda

Weakness versus geometry. Hold geometry roughly fixed and vary weakness. Evolve agents with the same sensor and actuator radius but different embodied policy spaces. The

prediction is that novelty survival tracks $|\mathcal{B}(\pi)|$ better than raw spatial span.

Chord-arpeggio tradeoff. Hold total accessible distinction budget roughly fixed while shifting between simultaneous and sequential realisation. The prediction is that task success tracks total accessible tone better than the naive time-space split, until the task truly requires co-instantiation.

Delegation. Fix the higher-layer task and progressively freeze lower layers. The prediction is that the higher-layer cone shrinks before the higher-layer geometry changes much.

Cone collapse. Construct hybrid collectives whose parts must maintain a nonempty policy intersection. Tighten top-down constraints until the intersection vanishes. The prediction is splintering into local strategies (Levin, 2021; Bennett, 2024a).

Basin width and resilience. Evolve homeostatic agents in environments with varying perturbation regimes. The prediction is that selection for resilience widens basins rather than strengthening convergence.

Unity beyond agency. Use simulated collectives with variable latency. The prediction is that collective agency persists beyond the point where a single unified subject remains possible (Bennett, 2026b,d).

Discussion

The ruler in context

Multiple traditions have circled the idea that adaptive systems benefit from keeping options open. The cybernetics of Wiener (1948) made variety central. Ashby's Law of Requisite Variety says a controller needs at least as much variety as the disturbances it faces (Ashby, 1957). Beer (1995) operationalised this in the Viable System Model. Empowerment (Klyubin et al., 2005) measures how much an agent can visibly change. The Free Energy Principle (Friston, 2010; Friston et al., 2023; Kirchhoff et al., 2018) predicts that adaptive systems minimise surprise, which under a viability prior reduces to keeping options open (Bennett, 2024a). Chollet (2019) proposed measuring intelligence by skill-acquisition efficiency over a broad task distribution. Kolchinsky and Wolpert (2018) formalised semantic information as information causally necessary for continued existence. Waddington's epigenetic landscape (Waddington, 1957) describes wide valleys as robust and narrow valleys as fragile. Camazine et al. (2001) documented how self-organisation produces robust collective outcomes from simple local rules. Deacon (2011) argued that what is absent can be as explanatory as what is present. Kauffman's adjacent possible (Kauffman, 2000) is the fringe of that absence. The extension is the whole interior. Vervaeke

et al. (2012) argued that cognition is fundamentally about relevance realisation, the ongoing process of determining what matters.

All of these point toward the same idea, but they don't quite get around to identifying the formal invariant. Weakness seems to be that missing formal invariant. It differs from requisite variety (which counts what a controller must possess, not what remains uncommitted), from empowerment (which can maximally dissociate from weakness), from description length (which is encoding-dependent), from Chollet's measure (which requires an external evaluator), and from the FEP (which it formally reduces to under viability assumptions but which does not by itself distinguish basin width from convergence strength). The unseen buffer $\mathcal{B}(\pi)$ is a combinatorial version of Kolchinsky's semantic information. Basin width is a formal version of Waddington's landscape. The physical limits on vocabulary size (Lloyd, 2000) constrain the maximum possible weakness. In reinforcement learning (Sutton and Barto, 2018), the distinction maps onto exploration versus exploitation. A policy that exploits aggressively has committed early. Its cone is narrow.

Summary

A cell's cognitive light cone, a neural network's generalisation capacity, and an evolving population's capacity for open-ended novelty are the same formal quantity measured in different substrates. That quantity is weakness. It is the number of completions compatible with a system's current commitments.

The ruler is about survival under novelty. It has consequences for three communities that have been working on the same problem without sharing a language. Weakness gives Levin's programme a formal size variable. It gives machine learning an encoding-independent generalisation measure. It gives artificial life a criterion for open-endedness. And it predicts that all three should respond to the same interventions. Cone-widening in biology, regularisation in ML, and slack-preserving selection in evolution are the same operation in different substrates.

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